

FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE THINKING OF GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOL STUDENTS

Mamadaliyev Ahadjon Ganiboyevich

*General education school No. 7, Chortoq district,
Namangan region, pre-service teacher*

Annotation: *This article contains methodological recommendations on the formation of modern thinking skills in students in general education schools and the formation of innovative thinking in educational conditions.*

Keywords: *Teacher, student, innovation, modern, school, methodological, traditional education, science and technology, intellectual.*

INTRODUCTION.

Addressing the issue of youth in our president's address to the Supreme Assembly on January 29, 2020: as we aim to turn Uzbekistan into a developed country, we will achieve this not only with rapid reforms, knowledge and innovation. To do this, first of all, it is necessary that we train a new generation of cadres who take the field as enterprising reformers, think strategically, are educated and qualified [1]- this appeal, in its essence, also determines that it is an important task of modern educators to educate the younger generation, studying in secondary schools, as intellectually gifted and creatively thinking.

In a rapidly developing world, it has become clear that traditional education, which believes that knowledge as the main task for raising an aspiring young generation, consists in giving a certain amount of knowledge, cannot respond to modern interpretation. Because science and technology have evolved to such an extent that now a person cannot keep even the most basic concepts in a science in his memory. On top of that, young people who are taking an independent step towards a life that has become one of relentless changes may not find their place in a world that consists of a struggle of rivalries if they are not prepared for such changes both intellectually and spiritually.

“innovation” “is derived from Latin (in-ga, novus-new), that is, the translation is” “update”, “mastering”, “introducing some kind of novelty”, “introducing a new one”, “innovating”. “In” new forms the main core of this concept.[2]

” Shaping students' innovative thinking skills issues preparing them for innovative activities A.Abdukodirov, N.Azizhodzhaeva, B.Adizov, N.Sayidahmedov, J.Yoldashev, F.Yuzlikaev, R.Djuraev, Sh.Mardonov, O'.Tolipov, D.Yunusova, S.Bozorova,

M.Jumaniyozova, Sh.Shodmonova, R.Safarova, A.Choriev, M.Quranov, O.Musurmonova, B.Farberman, S.Gulomov, U.It is reflected in the scientific research of the nishonalievans.

Therefore, human and technical resources for the purpose of optimizing educational models of pedagogical technology, taking into account their interaction, can be recognized as a system for creating, applying and identifying the entire process of teaching and mastering knowledge. Based on innovative educational technologies, on the basis of independent and creative thinking in the process of improving the creative shell of students, the formation of knowledge, skills and skills in children with hearing impairments, acquisition of knowledge related to the implementation of correctional and educational work in the process of special training, approach the process of special education with creative search, , provides for the development of skills for independent replenishment of their knowledge and qualifications.[3]

The goal is to get the highest possible result from the money and effort invested in the educational system or in the application of innovations in educational activities. The difference between innovation and any innovation is that it must have a variable mechanism that allows control and control. As in all areas, education speaks of “Novation”, “innovation”, as well as activities that express their essence.[4]

A.I.Prigozhin according to, innovation should be understood as a new approach to a certain social unit – organization, population, society, group-in a purposeful attitude, enriching this attitude with slightly stagnant elements. In this regard, it is understood that the author's views directly express the essence of social relations, an innovative approach to them. It follows that each individual, as a citizen, reader, specialist, leader, employee, in addition, as a participant in the process of various social relations, organizes its own innovative activities.[5]

American psychologist E.Rodgers studied in his research the socio-psychological aspects of social relations with an innovative character, the introduction of innovations in social relations, the categories of persons involved in this process, their relationship to innovation, the degree of acceptance of innovation, readiness to realize the essence, and the classification of social relations with an innovative character between certain categories of individuals. [6]

In modern education, innovation, more precisely, the use of pedagogical and Educational Innovations, is becoming more important. Consequently, globalization and the informatization of society dictate an innovative approach to the formation and practical use of educational materials, while dictating the use of effective methods and tools in non-traditional forms of the educational process.

Pedagogical innovation changes the internal structure of the pedagogical system. The ability of teachers of secondary schools to effectively, actively use pedagogical or

Educational Innovations takes place in a certain process. The innovative approach of educators to professional activities, while guaranteeing the achievement of the intended goal, helps to improve the quality and effectiveness of education, to strengthen the activity of acquiring knowledge in students.

In the educational system, the goal is to get the highest possible result from the money and effort invested in the application of innovations in educational activities. The difference between innovation and any innovation is that it must have a variable mechanism that allows control and control.

R. N. Yusufbekova focuses on considering innovations from a pedagogical point of view. In particular, it is emphasized by the author that pedagogical innovations are the content of a pedagogical phenomenon that may change in the course of education and training, leading to a previously unknown, unrecorded state or result.[7]

Hence, the structure of the innovative activity of the teacher consists of motivational, creative, technological and reflective components. Important systematic views on the structure of innovative activities, the justification of their tasks, the norms and levels of their formation are a necessary factor in their application to the practice of schools of Education [8].

Thus, in modern education, innovation, more precisely, the use of pedagogical and Educational Innovations, is becoming more important. Consequently, globalization and the informatization of society dictate an innovative approach to the formation and practical use of educational materials, while dictating the use of effective methods and tools in non-traditional forms of the educational process [9].

Innovative activity requires the acquisition of BKM based on directing the mental, mental, and physical strength of the pedagogue to a specific goal, supplementing practical activities with theoretical knowledge, developing knowledge, design, communicative speech, and organizational skills.

REFERENCES

1. *President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev's appeal to the Supreme Assembly of January 29, 2020.*
2. *Bespalco V.P.Advanced technologies of pedagogy and teaching. M.: Publishing house of the Institute of Professional Education of the Ministry of Defense of Russia, 1995.*
3. *Marschark M., G.Lang H., Albertini J. Educating deaf students. - Oxford University Press, 2006. P. 83.*
4. *Muslimov N.A., Usmanboyeva M.H., Sayfurov D.M., Torayev A.B. Innovative educational technologies. - Tashkent: 2015. - 208 pages.*
5. *Prigozhin A.I. Innovations: Incentives & Obstacles (1989)*

6. Rogers C. R. *Искусство консультирования и терапии*. – М.: Апрель, – С. 2002.-232.
7. Yusufbekova N.R. *General foundations of pedagogical innovation: experience in developing the theory of innovative processes in education / N.R. Yusufbekova*. - М.: Pedagogical Society, 1991. - 91 p.
8. Sharipova A.M. *“Important factors for the application of innovative activities to the practice of schools of education”*. *International Conference on Interdisciplinary Studies and Scientific Research Hosted online from Cambridge, London Date: 30th September, 2023*.
9. Sharipova A.M. *The content of the concepts of “innovative educational technologies” and “educational innovations”*. *Novateur publications international journal of innovations in engineering research and technology*. VOLUME 10, ISSUE 9, Sep. -2023.